

Role Of Digital Marketing In Creating New Entrepreneurs: A Case Study In Southern Odisha

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ABSTRACT

In the post covid era, Digital marketing has emerged as a revolutionary tool which utilizes ICT for business promotion. Easily available internet and smartphone at a price within the capacity of common man, has increased its use giving deep access of human society to the users of Digital Marketing through the means of various search engines and social media platforms.

Still lack of awareness among the people regarding digital marketing options and their potential in terms of providing alternate entrepreneurial opportunities and promoting the existing one in a better way than ever, is very low.

Present study focusses on understanding the role of digital marketing in promoting entrepreneurship among the people. The study is based on the primary data collected from the south Odisha region of India. The study is done by collecting responses from more than 450 entrepreneurs of the region and understanding their perception about digital marketing and the pattern of use of digital marketing. Number of entrepreneurs who emerged as the one with the help of digital marketing are identified and the conclusion is drawn.

Keywords: - Digital Marketing, Entrepreneurship development, Entrepreneurship, Digital Entrepreneurship, Internet Marketing.

1. Introduction: -

Entrepreneurs' newer avenues for transforming society and the economy in their innovative and growth-enhancing roles are vital. The digital marketing initiatives contributing to such strategies for creating new entrepreneurs could be a vital tool for socio-economic development challenges. In the era of information technology, the increasing role of digital marketing and its growing share of marketing budgets have been bridging the demand-supply gap through a customer-oriented approach for economic reforms, performance improvement, and social advancements. The role of effective digital marketing in shaping entrepreneurial talents is imperative in today's dynamic world. The new generation Management Information System, with a business intelligence focus on various technological inputs for customer engagement and communication tools, has become an attractive function for empowering general choice opportunities in the entrepreneurial society. Against this backdrop, the survey study is undertaken to explore how digital marketing practices are shaping entrepreneurial interests in southern Odisha.

2. Literature Review:

In her paper "A Study on Use of Digital Marketing by Entrepreneurs," Dr. C. Kala (2020) stated that the growing usage of social media and internet platforms has encouraged business owners to use them as a means of turning ideas into brands. He saw that the market for online sales was predicted to grow from \$2.5 billion in 2009 to \$56 billion in 2023. He also came to the conclusion that, in the midst of the pandemic, digital marketing has given business owners new ways to engage with and keep consumers.

Cliff Wymbs (2011) stated that the need for an evolution of the academic architecture of business and marketing curriculum has arisen due to the economy's rapid digitalisation and the world's rapid change in his paper "Digital Marketing: The Time for a New "Academic Major" Has Arrived." He asserted that the way marketing and business are conducted has changed as a result of the usage of social media and the internet. He placed special emphasis on identifying the difficulties and strategies for implementing the curriculum at the launch of a new digital marketing major in business and marketing education.

In their 2017 work, "Growth of a Platform Business Model as an Entrepreneurial Ecosystem and its Effects on Regional Development," JinHyo Joseph Yun et al. examined the factors that influence the dynamics of platform business models and how to characterise them. They also determined how this business model affected the expansion of the region.

In their paper "Impact of digital marketing development on entrepreneurship," Kenzhegul Bizhanova et al. (2019) came to the conclusion that digital marketing aids in managing competition, boosting sales, and drawing in a sizable audience with greater accuracy and fewer resources.

The impact of digitisation on the Indian entrepreneurial ecosystem was examined by Ashish Gupta et al. (2020) in their paper "Impact of digitisation on entrepreneurial ecosystems: an Indian perspective." They recognised the need for research on the effects of digitisation on both new and established organisations, as well as the role that public policy and government play in supporting the development of sustainable ventures.

In their paper "Social Media Marketing and Business Performance of MSMEs During the COVID-19 Pandemic," Jahid Syaifullah et al. (2021) pointed out that MSMEs can enhance their performance by managing social media more effectively. The study examined how MSMEs in Indonesia used social media, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. They discovered that a number of factors, including perceived ease of use, cost, compatibility, and other enabling conditions, influence how often people use social media. In their paper "The Main Factors Influencing E-Business Technology Adoption of Entrepreneurs in WOW Project Songkhla, Thailand," Wanamina Bostan Ali and Sumana Laparokit (2019) discovered that a number of factors contribute to the acceptance of the E-Business model, with performance expectancy having the greatest influence.

Rukanda, Kaniati & Samsudin (2021) in their paper "Efforts to Strengthen Mental Entrepreneurs Through Online Based Digital Marketing Training for Youth of Productive Age" used descriptive method and qualitative approach to identify the level of use of social media by youth and to determine the process of online digital marketing training for youth. They identified that the training program has helped in improving the standard of living of the people.

In their paper "The Role of Digital Marketing in Assisting Small Rural Entrepreneurs Amidst Covid-19 Movement Control Order (MCO): A Case Study in Peninsular Malaysia," Abdul Rashid et al. (2021) noted that it is critical to comprehend how digital marketing helped small businesses during the pandemic establish new business norms. They conducted a quantitative study with 158 small rural business owners from Penang, Malaysia, utilising the snowball sampling approach. They came to the conclusion that small business owners recognise the value of using digital platforms for their operations.

Ukpere, Celestine Lugaye; Slabbert, Andre D.; Ukpere, Wilfred I. (2014) in their paper titled "Rising Trend in Social Media Usage by Women Entrepreneurs across the Globe to Unlock Their Potentials for Business Success" observed that marketers now understand the power and importance of internet as a tool of communication. They concluded in their study that use of social media platforms by women entrepreneurs at any level has boosted their financial success and has helped them in various ways to develop and effectively manage their business.

Ratten, V. and Rashid, S. (2021), in their paper "Entrepreneurship Education and Digital Marketing: What Does the Future Hold?" discussed the need of embedding more digital marketing techniques in entrepreneurship education. They argued that both Digital Marketing and digital entrepreneurship have a lot in common and

teaching digital marketing as a part of entrepreneurship education has become more important during COVID-19 pandemic where most of the entrepreneurship programs are running in online or digital mode.

Redondo, Remedios Pitre; de Avila, William Manjarres; Palma, Hugo Hernandez (2018) in their paper “Digital marketing as a promoter of entrepreneurship in the footwear sector in Colombia” identified the impact of Digital marketing on the footwear industry of Columbia combining both the qualitative and quantitative techniques. They concluded that the use of information and communication technology (ICT) in the sector shows growth opportunities and at the same time they also focused on the importance of education and training regarding the same.

Neetu Jalan, Vijayendra Gupta (2020) in their paper “Scope, Opportunity and Challenges to Digital Entrepreneurship” observes that because of the growing competition Digital marketing is no more a trend but a necessity to survive in the market and beat competition.

Christina, I. D., Fenni, F., & Roselina, D. (2019) in their paper “Digital marketing strategy in promoting product” studied the strategies and role related to various channels of digital marketing in promoting products. They discussed about the uniqueness of the strategy and its importance in Product promotion.

Gartanti, W. T., Triwardhani, I. J., & Putra, R. P. (2020, March) in their research titled “The Development of Village Entrepreneurship Through Digital Marketing Communication” observed that marketing the products digitally on any platform needs technical skills and ability to design impressive content to communicate well and attract the consumers’ attention

3. Research Gap: -

The use of Digital Marketing by existing entrepreneurs, reasons behind it, and its implications has been studied by many researchers, which shows the utility of digital marketing as a leading tool of marketing with several advantages. However, if the said tool is playing any role in attracting youth to choose entrepreneurship as a career is yet to be studied.

4. Research Objectives: -

- To understand impact of digital marketing on youth in choosing entrepreneurship as a career option.
- To identify trend of choosing new entrepreneurial options created by Digital Marketing (like youtubing or Blogging).
- To identify the reasons behind the gap between the potential and actual result if any.
- To suggest for betterment in the same.

5. Methodology: -

Research methodology involves collection of primary data through questionnaire distribution, Personal interview and interaction with the people. Around 451 responses were received and analyzed to understand the trends about the perceived impact of digital Marketing on business.

6. Results & Discussions: -

Digital marketing provides many other options for aspiring entrepreneurs to launch their startups in various ways. These are discussed categorically below:-

1. **Digital Marketing's Impact on Entrepreneurial Growth:** The research revealed that digital marketing significantly reduces the minimum budget required for marketing, allowing entrepreneurs to start businesses with as little as ₹1000, a massive advantage compared to traditional methods. This low-cost entry point has enabled broader market access, both nationally and internationally.
2. **Increased Work-from-Home Opportunities:** Digital marketing allows entrepreneurs to operate remotely, eliminating the need for physical office space and reducing infrastructure costs. This has fostered a culture of work-from-home, further enhancing the flexibility and scalability of businesses.
3. **Diverse Revenue Streams for Entrepreneurs:** Beyond regular business operations, digital marketing offers various new avenues for earning, including affiliate marketing, blogging, YouTube, social media

influencing, and content marketing. These options require minimal investment, encouraging solopreneurship and providing opportunities for self-employment.

4. **Adoption of Digital Marketing Post-COVID:** A significant number of entrepreneurs adopted digital marketing in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Out of 451 respondents, 69 reported recently turning to digital marketing to sustain their businesses during the economic disruption caused by the pandemic.
5. **Entrepreneurs' Positive Perception of Digital Marketing:** Most respondents (345 out of 451) acknowledged that digital marketing is essential for business success. Additionally, 153 respondents attested that it has improved their business returns, highlighting its effectiveness as a tool for growth.
6. **Uneven Awareness and Adoption:** Despite its benefits, a sizable portion of the population remains unaware of digital marketing's potential. Out of 451 respondents, 184 have not yet adopted digital marketing practices, indicating a gap in awareness and usage.
7. **Digital Marketing as a Catalyst for New Business Models:** The emergence of new professions directly linked to digital marketing, such as e-commerce selling, content creation, and website design, underscores the role of digital marketing in fostering entrepreneurial opportunities. Approximately 132 entrepreneurs were involved in these fields, with YouTubing being the most prominent.

On collection and analysis of Data we were able to derive the following results:

Figure -1 Number of Entrepreneurs using Digital Marketing

Out of the 451 responses received 174 entrepreneurs use digital marketing to promote their business while 187 of them are still in planning phase for the same.

Figure -2 When did the entrepreneurs started using Digital marketing

In their responses 112 entrepreneurs said that they are using digital marketing since the beginning. Around 86 of them admitted that they started business with the help of digital marketing as it lowered down the cost of start-up. Around 69 of them have started using the digital marketing recently and some 86 of them have started using it after 1 year of establishment of their business. Out of those who started using it recently are mostly those who were hit by the COVID-19 pandemic. Still 184 out of 451 are not using Digital marketing till today.

Figure -3 Entrepreneurs considering Digital marketing to be essential for business

When asked about the essentiality of digital marketing for business success 345 out of 451 admitted that it is essential tool today while 21 still consider it to be a dispensable tool. 77 respondents were not very sure about it.

Figure -3 Entrepreneurs considering Digital marketing has improved their business returns.

When talked about impact of digital marketing on their business 153 respondents of those who use digital marketing options admitted that it is an effective tool and has improved their business performance while some 12 of them were having a opposite picture in their mind. Remaining respondents said that they are not sure of the impact of digital marketing on their business.

Figure -4 Pattern of entrepreneurs involved in various digital marketing options.

Out of the 174 entrepreneurs who are using digital marketing 132 are those who are into the fields that emerged because of the digital marketing (discussed in detail under section 6.3 and section 6.6).

While the pie chart above shows the distribution pattern among the various options. The table below tells about the number of respondents in each field.

Field of work	no. of respondents involved
Affiliate Marketing	9
Blogging	10
Content development	3
Digital Marketing agency	12
Selling through E-commerce platform	23
Social Media Influencing	11
Website designing	14
Youtubing	50
None	42
Total	174

Table -1 Number of entrepreneurs involved in various digital marketing options

The above table and the pie chart clearly mentions that Digital Marketing has fostered entrepreneurial mindset among the people and has promoted entrepreneurship in the society.

Conclusion: -

The study concludes that digital marketing is a powerful enabler of entrepreneurship in Southern Odisha. By lowering the entry barriers and providing scalable, cost-effective marketing tools, it has democratized business opportunities for individuals with limited resources.

While digital marketing has shown great potential in promoting entrepreneurship, there is a critical need for increased awareness and education. The study recommends that policymakers and business organizations implement targeted training programs to ensure that more people can benefit from digital marketing tools and strategies.

Given the positive results from early adopters, there is significant potential for further entrepreneurial growth in the region if digital literacy and infrastructure continue to improve. The research suggests that focused initiatives on digital skills training can contribute to long-term socio-economic development.

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